

Studies on the Heteropoly Tantalatotungstate (VI)

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The nature of formation and conditions of preparation of heteropoly tantalatotungstate (VI) has been established by studying pH changes and thermometric titrimetry. The composition has been established by chemical and instrumental methods. The analytical values agreed with the formula $K_6Na_4[WTa_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 17H_2O$. The molecular weight of the compound was determined by cryoscopic method. The important data of X-ray powder photography of the compound have been shown in the powder file. The pressure-composition isothermal have been studied in solid phase at 35° and 45°. From the isothermals the stablest form came down to $K_6Na_4[WTa_{12}O_{36}] \cdot 6H_2O$.

LAPITSKII and his coworkers¹ reported the heteropoly tantalate complexes of several transitional metal ions and also of Ce (III). Dale, Buckley and Pope² have examined some of these complexes and in general have not found the Russian work to be reproducible.

Experimental

Regarding the preparation a reference to the old and contemporary chemical literature would clearly show that the methods are based on trial and error or on conjecture. So this investigation, attempts to lay down some rigid conditions of preparations. Arbitrary concentrations of the reactants may cause immediate precipitation or a complete reaction leading to the formation of the compounds with indefinite composition. Therefore to start with, solution of *M*/50 orthohexatantalate and *M*/20 sodium tungstate was found to be workable. The variation of pH changes were recorded against the volume, when *M*/50 potassium orthohexatantalate solution was gradually added into 60 ml of *M*/20 sodium tungstate solution. To corroborate the experimental observations, help was taken from the application of thermometric titrimetry³ also. The results are recorded in Figs. 1 and 2. By comparing these two graphs the range in volume of the reactants could be studied.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

So, the amounts in terms of volume marked from graphs were considered and the point of the horizontal line was taken into consideration as the limiting amounts to be taken for 60 ml of *M*/20 sodium tungstate solution. Hence 30 ml of *M*/50 K-orthohexatantalate was refluxed with 60 ml of *M*/20 sodium tungstate solution for about an hour. The solution was then evaporated slowly on a water bath and left overnight, when white powder like compound separated which was collected and dried. For estimation of tantalum and tungsten by chemical method, they are to be separated first. This separation was based on the precipitation of tantalic acid by ammonium-magnesium salt solution⁴ when tungsten remained dissolved in the solution. Tantalum was then estimated from the precipitate as Ta_2O_5 and from the filtrate tungsten was estimated as WO_3 by the use of tannin and cinchonine hydrochloride⁵.

Colorimetric analyses of tantalum and tungsten were also done by pyragallol and toluene 3,4-dithiol

respectively at 450 m μ and 400 m μ . For the estimation of sodium and potassium, they were separated first, then potassium was estimated by perchloric method⁷ and sodium by Zn-uranyl acetate method.

The experimental results are tabulated :

Element	% found		Mean	% calculated
<i>Tungsten</i>				
Chemical	5.10	5.10	5.11	5.11
Colorimetric	5.11	5.11		
<i>Tantalum</i>				
Chemical	60.38	60.37	60.37	60.38
Colorimetric	60.37	60.38		
<i>Sodium</i>				
Chemical	2.55	2.55	2.54	2.55
Flame photometric	2.55	2.55		
<i>Potassium</i>				
Chemical	6.51	6.51	6.51	6.52
Flame photometric	6.52	6.52		
<i>Water & Oxygen</i> (by difference)	25.45	25.45	25.45	25.45

From the above percentage composition data, the molecular formula of the compound came to $K_6Na_4[WTa_{12}O_{38}]17H_2O$. According to I.U.P.A.C. system⁹ the compound has been named as heteropoly tantalatotungstate (VI).

Determination of Pressure-Composition isothermals : The apparatus used for this purpose has been described by Ray and Sinha¹⁰ and Bhattacharya.¹¹ Isothermal at 35° in stepwise dissociation process gave rise to two systems with respect to water which came to 17H₂O/8H₂O and 8H₂O/7H₂O whereas the isothermal at 45° in stepwise dissociation process gave rise to two systems with respect to water which came to 17H₂O/8H₂O and 8H₂O/6H₂O. This piece of work indicated that between 35° to 45° only 6H₂O remained as the well bound water molecules.

Determination of molecular weight : To get some approximate idea about the molecular weight, the cryoscopic method has been applied in pure water as a solvent. This approximation was satisfactory because all the sodium and potassium ions will not ordinarily ionise.^{12,15} The anionic weight came to 2746 against the theoretically calculated value 2963.25. In the previous communication¹² it has been shown how the determination of cell-dimension by X-ray diffraction could be useful to calculate the molecular weight of the compound. But for the failure to obtain a sharp single crystal of the compound, Weissenberg's X-ray crystal diffraction method could not be applied in this case.

X-ray powder diffraction : The data on X-ray powder diffraction have been considered to be very much useful for the elucidation of structures and phases of heteropoly compounds. But the reports on standard powder files are very few¹³. The relevant data as obtained for tantalatotungstate (VI) from a powder photograph have been entered in the form of a standard powder card in Table 2. On the first line of the card the interplaner spacing of the three

TABLE 2

d	7.8	3.25	3.0	12.0	$K_6Na_4[WTa_{12}O_{38}]17H_2O_9$ Heteropoly tantalatotungstate (VI)					
I/I-	100	72	54	16	dÅ	I/I-	hkl	dÅ	I/I-	hkl
Ra CuK α ;	$\alpha = 1.5405$				1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.
Filter-Ni					12.0	16		3.25	54	
I/I-Visual strip measurement					11.0	20		3.15	15	
Ref. Nil					10.1	22		3.11	6	
System					9.7	40		3.04	6	
					9.2	14		3.00	54	
					8.6	22		2.80	16	
					7.8	100		2.72	16	
					7.2	36		2.65	6	
					6.9	14		2.60	6	
					6.6	33		2.52	15	
					6.2	33		2.45	6	
					5.4	22		2.30	15	
					5.2	20		2.25	16	
					4.8	6		2.20	17	
					4.65	42		2.06	6	
					4.25	22		2.02	14	
					3.95	35		1.97	6	
					3.7	24		1.93	15	
					3.52	14		1.84	14	
					3.48	14		1.78	6	
					3.38	14		1.58	6	
					.30	314				

X-ray powder file of tantalatotungstate (VI).

most intense lines are arranged in order of the decreasing intensities; the fourth 'd' value is the largest observed spacing. The relative intensities (I/I₁) of these reflections are based on 100 for the strongest intensity observed are listed on the next line; directly below the corresponding 'd' values. The other lines of the card are self-explanatory.

Discussion

The general belief for condensation process of heteropoly acids is, that the maintenance of the acidic medium is a must. But the important part of the present observation is the formation of the compound $K_6Na_4[WTa_{12}O_{38}]17H_2O$ in basic medium for pH value 11.6 (graph No. 1). This sort of condensation in presence of OH group may be compared with the catalytic behaviour of the OH group in basic

Fig. 3

aldol condensation. It may be predicted that in the formation of this type of heteropoly compound,

'OH' behaves as catalyst and the resultant might be the polyhedra of the oxides of tantalum and tungsten by the elimination of H_2O molecule. Indication may be had from the reports of X-ray studies on isopoly anion $[Ta_6O_{19}]^{8-}$ wherein Lindqvist and others¹⁴⁻¹⁵ pointed out a sort of projection pattern of tantalum and oxygen.

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